

Effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy in Reducing Suicidal Ideation among University Undergraduate Students in Delta State

Helen O. Eboigbe

Department of Guidance and Counselling, Delta State University, Abraka Nigeria

Dr A. E. Oghounu

Department of Guidance and Counselling, Delta State University, Abraka Nigeria

Prof (Mrs) E. E. Eбенуwa-Okoh

Department of Guidance and Counselling, Delta State University, Abraka Nigeria

Abstract

This study examined the Effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy in reducing Suicidal ideation among Undergraduate Student in Delta State Public Universities. Three null hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental design using a pre-test post-test control group was adopted. The population consisted of 472 undergraduate students with a history of suicidal ideation in the six public universities in Delta State. The sample size consisted of all 243 students, selected from three of the six public universities in Delta State. The purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used. The instrument that was used for data collection, screening and selection of participants was a questionnaire titled: Suicidal Ideation Rating Scale (SIRS). The instrument was validated by 3 experts. The reliability of the instrument was established by administering the questionnaire to 100 undergraduate students with history of suicidal ideation in Delta State. Paired and independent samples t-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of participants expose to REBT treatment; there was no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of participants in the control group; and that there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of participants expose to REBT and the Control Group. On the basis of these finding, it was recommended amongst others, that Guidance Counsellors should expand the use of REBT in mental health services, particularly targeting individuals with high levels of suicidal ideation.

Keywords: Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy; Suicidal Ideation; University Undergraduate; Students.

Introduction

The most valuable offering a country can provide to its citizens is education, primarily aimed at instilling important values, attitudes, and social knowledge. This serves the purpose of enabling individuals to effectively interact with both their peers and the broader society. Nigeria's education system encompasses three different sectors: Basic Education (made up of Lower basic, three years; middle basic, three years; and upper basic, three years), Senior Secondary Education (Three years), and Tertiary Education (four to six years, depending on the program of study). Attending a university can be an exciting and dynamic experience, it can also present some challenges. Outside of the obvious academic pressures, students may have to deal with stresses related to physical or mental illness (such as, depression, anxiety), family issues, time management, moving away from home, financial concerns and a host of others. In higher educational institutions, undergraduates sometimes feel overwhelmed or discouraged as they encounter various life and academic challenges which could lead to suicide among the students.

Suicide could be seen as the act of forcefully taking one's own life as a result of psychosocial unattainable or unaddressed pressing issues. This could also be interpreted as a severe and impulsive choice to end one's own life, as a means to break free from persistent and overwhelming life challenges, especially when it seems that there is no possibility of survival or escape. Suicide has been ranked as the 11th major leading factor that leads to death in 2020

which has the capacity to exterminate the life of more than 31,655 individuals which could be subject to the level of depression, oppression and social and biological demands in each of the years. Suicidal is intentional. It is planned and executed. It is the act and process of taking one's life by force (Tuoyo-Olulu & Oghounu, 2024).

Suicide is a serious public health problem; responsible for 1.48% of deaths worldwide (Institute of Health Metrics & Evaluation, 2016). The prevalence is significantly greater in adolescents and young adults, comprising 8.64% of fatalities in the 20-24 age group (Institute of Health Metrics & Evaluation, 2016), and stands as the third most common cause of death among 15-24 year-olds (Aria, et al., 2009). University students, in particular, appear to be disproportionately affected when compared to the general population, as evidenced by numerous media and newspaper reports highlighting cases of suicide among this demographic. Abiogun, (2019) and Dachew et al (2015), discovered in their study that academic and social pressures as well as new social environment and financial burden mounted on the student could be responsible for a high rate of suicidal ideation among undergraduate student. Moreover, common risk factors for suicide such as mental and substance use disorders are very common among university students (Atwoli et al, 2011). Suicidal ideation among university students have been a concern to student, parents, government, and the university management (Branden, 2019) and have been traced to some socio-demographic variables such as age and sex.

Suicidal ideation refers to thoughts or considerations about ending one's own life. These thoughts can range from fleeting considerations to detailed planning and intent to commit suicide. Suicidal ideation can be passive (thinking about death or wishing to be dead without specific plans) or active (having specific plans or the intent to attempt suicide). It is

often a sign of serious emotional distress, depression, or other mental health issues and may require immediate attention or intervention to prevent harm. The components include hopelessness, loneliness, family background, poor relationship, substance use, trapped, purposelessness, recklessness, mood and personal factor (Obi & Oghounu, 2023).

Suicidal ideation whether attempted or completed is detrimental to the health, physical, emotional and spiritual well-being of such an individual. Suicidal ideation is a powerful inclination that compels an individual to take their own life. It is as a result of self-defeating thoughts and feelings that are unfounded and unjustifiable. It is filled with perplexing questions about why life is so grim and intolerable. People with suicidal thoughts and ideations are supposed to be helped out of the situation and brought to realities of life. This state of suicidal ideation among undergraduate student required great deal of behavioural and cognitive repositioning. Other interventions, such as Reality Therapy by William Glasser, Emotional Intelligence Therapy, and Solution-Focused Brief Therapy, have been employed to reduce suicidal ideation. However, the researcher intends to explore the use of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT) to assess its potential in reducing suicidal thoughts among undergraduate students (Oyibo & Oghounu, 2023).

Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy (REBT) was propounded by Albert Ellis in the year 1957 as an educational process in which the therapist teaches the client how to identify irrational and self-defeating beliefs and philosophies which in nature are rigid, extreme, unrealistic, illogical and absolutist, and then replace them with more rational and self-helping beliefs. By using different cognitive, emotive and behavioral methods and activities, the client, together with help from the therapist and in homework exercises, can gain a more rational, self-

helping and constructive rational way of thinking and behaving. One of the main objectives in REBT is to show the client that whenever unpleasant and unfortunate activating events occur in people's lives, they have a choice of making themselves feel healthier and self-helpingly happy, or making themselves feel unhealthily and self-defeating horrified, terrified, panicked, depressed, self-hating and self-pitying. It focuses on the fact that human thinking, emotions and actions are expressed simultaneously. REBT focuses on resolving emotional and behavioural problems. REBT therapeutic strategy involves the use of ABCDE model where A is the events, B is the belief about the event, C the consequences as a result of B, and D, the disputing and debating of B and E, the new and acceptable thoughts and beliefs. It is believed that REBT can actively dispute adaptive and suicidal thoughts and beliefs that can impact negatively on one's emotion as it has proved effective in reducing maladaptive behaviour among adolescents (Khaledian, et al, 2013; Ekechukwu, 2018)

The researcher proposed to examine the potential effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy (REBT) in reducing suicidal ideation among university students. While REBT has shown promise in various studies for improving mental health by addressing irrational beliefs and depressive symptoms, which are often associated with suicidal thoughts, its specific impact on suicidal ideation among university students remained underexplored. While some research has evaluated various therapies in reducing suicidal ideation, direct comparisons between REBT and other therapeutic interventions in the context of university students had not been comprehensively explored. Therefore, this study filled this gap by assessing whether REBT is effective in reducing suicidal ideation, in comparison to other therapeutic modalities that have been employed in similar contexts.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT treatment.
2. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants exposed to the Control Group.
3. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT and the Control Group.

Methods

The quasi-experimental design using a pre-test post-test control group was used in this study. One experimental group (Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy) and one control group were involved in the study. The target population of the study consisted of 472 undergraduate students who had visited the counselling center and with a history of suicidal ideation in the six public universities in Delta State. A purposive sample of 243 participants was selected from the target population for this study, comprising individuals from three universities that were randomly chosen from the six public universities in Delta State. The subjects are current students that have been diagnosed of suicidal ideation in the various counselling centre in the selected universities. The universities were selected through a simple random sampling technique. One public university was selected each from the three senatorial Districts making a total of three universities. In other words, the name of all the universities in a senatorial district were written on a piece of paper, folded and placed in a container. The researcher

shuffled the container, picked one from it and unfolded it to show the university written on it. This was done until all three universities were selected.

The instrument that was used for data collection, screening and selection of participants was a questionnaire titled: Suicidal Ideation Rating Scale (SIRS). The scale was adapted from the Geriatric Suicide Ideation Scale (GSIS), developed by Heisel and Flett (2006). The scale is a multi-dimensional measure of suicide-related ideation and associated factors developed for use with adults. It is a 28 items scale, measured on a 4-point scale. It focuses on five components namely suicidal ideation, perceived life orientation, loss of personal and social worth and death ideation. The instrument is made up of two sections. First section consisted of items on respondents' demographics such as sex, age, and level of study of undergraduate final year student. The second sections contained the SIRS.

The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation in the Faculty of Education, Delta State University Abraka. They ascertained the face validity of the instrument and to establish if the items in the instrument were relevant to the problem of the study. Some errors were pointed out and all corrections will be effected by the researcher and the instrument will be accepted as valid. Factor analysis was used to ensure the content and construct validity of the instrument. The principal component analysis of the extraction method was used to estimate the content validity of the instrument. The explained variance includes 67.13% for Suicidal Ideation Rating Scale; and 43.57% for Self-Esteem Rating Scale. These values expressed the content validity of the various scales. The rotated factor loading of the varimax method was used to estimate the construct validity of the instrument. It yielded the following values; 0.67-0.86 for Suicidal Ideation Rating Scale; and 0.56-0.79 for Self-Esteem

Rating Scale. These values expressed the construct validity of the various scales. Before the pilot study, the instrument had a total of 38 items (28 items for Suicidal Ideation Rating Scale; and 10 items for Self-Esteem Rating Scale). However, after the item analysis, a total of 22 items (16 items for Suicidal Ideation Rating Scale; and 6 for Self-Esteem Rating Scale). In determining the reliability of the Suicidal ideation among Undergraduate Student Inventory (SRUSI) and Rosenberg' Self-esteem Scale (RSS), the researcher administered one hundred (100) copies of the instrument to other undergraduate students with same history of suicidal ideation other than the target population in Delta State. who were not part of the main study but were considered equivalent in nature. The internal consistency of the instruments was determined by analysing the data collected using Cronbach's Alpha statistics and an alpha value of $r=0.72$ ($p<0.001$) was obtained for Suicidal ideation among Undergraduate Student Inventory (SRUSI).

The researchers presented a letter of introduction to the Dean of each faculty that were selected for the study in each public universities in Delta State. This was to enable the researchers obtain an approval to use 300 level undergraduate students for the research purpose. The researchers were assisted by three (3) research assistants who were given detailed training on the administration of the treatment packages (REBT and MHAP). The research assistants helped in the administration and collection of the research instrument, distribution of treatment materials and in the supervision of participants during treatment session. The researchers explained some of the items in the research instrument to the participants. This enabled the participants to have a clear understanding and fill the right options as it affected

them. As soon as they were through with the exercise, the completed questionnaires was collected.

The study was carried out in three stages: the pre-test, treatment, and post-test stages.

Pre-test (Stage 1)

The pre-test stage was carried out on the first day where the researcher was introduced to the participants of the study and thereafter the researcher and the research assistants administered the questionnaires on all the participants in the experimental and control groups before treatment. This was done to identify students who had a high suicidal ideation which constitutes a focal group. Data collected formed the baseline and was compared to the post-test scores, within and between the experimental and control groups. The pre-test stage lasted for forty-five (45) minutes per session. The researcher established rapport with the students to create a cordial relationship, confidence, and enabling environment to sustain interest and commitment throughout the programme. This was achieved by displaying warmth, good humour, smiles, and communication of lovable, approachable, and acceptable behaviour verbally and non-verbally.

Treatment (Stage 2)

The second stage in the experimental procedure was the treatment or exposure of the experimental group to the specified Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy. The Control Group did not receive any treatment. The treatment for the experimental group started a week after the pre-test and it lasted for six (6) weeks. There were 12 treatment sessions, two treatment sessions held per week for the experimental groups. The treatment sessions took place at the

venue that was convenient for both the researcher and the participants. Refreshments like cold drinks and snacks were given to all the participants at the end of each treatment session. Also, notepad and pen was distributed.

Post-test (Stage 3)

After the treatments had been administered to the participants, the students in the two groups (experimental and control groups) were post-tested and their results were compared with that of the pre-test and this took place on the last week of the treatment stage.

Treatment Packages in the Experimental Groups

There were three treatment packages namely:

1. Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy
2. Control Group

The participants were randomly assigned to each of the two groups. The researcher met with each group twice a week for six weeks (two sessions per week). The groups were tagged A and B. Group A received the REBT treatment while group C received non-attention treatment. The participants in each group who finally completed the treatment session in the two groups were post-tested by administering the same instrument used for the pre-test, after which their results were compared at the end of the treatment procedure.

REBT treatment programme for Experimental Group A

The REBT treatment was conducted for a period of six weeks of two sessions per week, numbering up to twelve sessions of 45 minutes per session. The objective of this programme was to assist affected undergraduate students manage suicidal ideation which could lead to premature death. To this end, affected undergraduate student were exposed to relevant issues in each session listed below:

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Session 1: Orientation and familiarization of the researcher/research assistants/participants;

The researcher exchanged pleasantries with participants, introduced herself and her research assistants, introduced the programme to the participants, encouraged them to participate fully throughout all the session, assured them of the need for confidentiality, and solicited for their cooperation to bring about future success. The research instrument was administered to obtain pretest score. After the participants finished responding to the items in the instrument, it was retrieved on the spot.

Sessions 2: Definition of Problem and Illustration. The students were exposed to the nature of suicidal ideation, its signs and symptoms, causes and its effect on academic performance and well-being

Session 3: The participant were exposed to the ABC Model by Beck. This session aimed at explaining the ABC of Becks Cognitive Model. In the ABC model: A, stand for activating event meaning (something has happened); B, for belief about what has happened (the event); and C for consequences of the emotional reaction to that belief. Students were also taught to identify the underlying irrational thoughts, feeling, and behaviour of the individual with suicidal ideation.

Session 4: Understanding the links between thoughts, feelings, and behaviour. Students were taught how their thoughts, feelings, and behaviour are connected.

Session 5: Practical application of the ABC'S of rational emotive behaviour therapy to suicidal ideation

Session 6: Disputing Irrational Thoughts and Identifying Thinking Errors

Session 7: Imagery. Participants were able to define imagery as well as list the uses of imagery which include: Relaxation, Meditate, improve mood, future personal performance, and development

Session 8: Finding Alternative Thoughts. At the end of the session, participants were able to find alternative balanced thoughts as against unhelpful thinking habit activities

Session 9: Participants were exposed to Wise mind and Positive Affirmations. At the end of the session, participants were able to define: what Wise Mind means and to comprehend positive statements that could help them develop a new attitude toward themselves and their situations.

Session 10: In this session, participants were taught The Worry Tree. The researcher drew the worry tree and explained it to the participants: the researcher went further to explain to the participants that any situation they do not have control over, they just have to accept it as part of their life. They should also worry less about what others say, think, and feel about them. Let worry go, and change the focus of attention.

Session 11: The participants were exposed to Distancing or diffusing from irrational thoughts. The researcher led the participants to practice how to distance or diffuse irrational thoughts. Diffusing from our thoughts involves acknowledging the thoughts as a thought, not reacting automatically, and then choosing to put our focus of attention elsewhere by learning mindful breathing and practice.

Session 12: The participant were taught positive steps of wellbeing and how to take that step; that is, being kind to oneself, encouraging rather than criticizing oneself. Participants were also taught how to treat themselves the way they would treat a friend in the same situation.

Post-test: The research instrument was administered to obtain post-test scores; the participants were given enough time to respond to the items in the instrument and after they were through, the instrument was retrieved. The results were compared with that of the pre-test result.

Control Group B

The participants in the control group received a non-attention treatment. The participants in this group were only pre-tested with the same instrument used for the participants in the experimental groups. The participants, however, were not given any treatment. At the end of six weeks they were again exposed to the same instrument to get the post-test scores. The scores from the tests were statistically analyzed in order to establish the effectiveness of the therapies employed in the study.

Data Analysis

Data collected in this study were analysed inferential statistics. Paired and independent samples t-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The analysis was carried out with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants exposed to REBT treatment

Table 1: t-test analysis of the difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants exposed to REBT treatment

Scores	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
Pre-Test Scores	141	52.11	10.59	140	82.61	.000	Significant
Post-Test Scores	141	29.09	7.29				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4.1 shows a paired-samples t-test, which was conducted to examine the difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT treatment. From the table, the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance ($t = 82.61, p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is, therefore, rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT treatment.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants in the control group

Table 4.2: t-test analysis of the difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants in the control group

Scores	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P</i>	Remark
Pre-Test Scores	57	54.14	10.06	56	1.76	.083	Not Significant
Post-Test Scores	57	53.61	10.56				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 2 shows a paired-samples t-test, which was conducted to examine the difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants in the control group. From the table, the p-value of 0.083 was greater than 0.05 level of significance ($t = 1.76, p > 0.05$). The null hypothesis is, therefore, accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants in the control group.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT and the Control Group

Table 3: Analysis of the difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT and the Control Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
REBT	141	29.09	7.29				
Control Group	57	53.61	10.56	196	16.06	.000	Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 3 shows an independent samples t-test done to test the difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT and the Control Group. The table shows that the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance ($t = 16.06, p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT and the Control Group. From the result, students exposed to REBT treatment have a lower mean score.

Discussions

The first finding revealed that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants expose to REBT treatment. This finding suggests that REBT is an effective intervention for reducing suicidal thoughts. This significant difference indicates that the participants experienced a measurable decline in suicidal ideation following the treatment. The use of pre-test and post-test measurements allows for a clear comparison, showing that the change in scores is not due to chance but likely due to the intervention.

The above finding underscores the potential of REBT to address and mitigate the cognitive and emotional factors contributing to suicidal ideation. By helping individuals

identify and challenge irrational beliefs, REBT facilitates the development of healthier, more rational thought patterns. This cognitive restructuring can lead to a decrease in the intensity and frequency of suicidal thoughts, as evidenced by the significant reduction in mean scores from pre-test to post-test. Moreover, the finding supports the broader application of REBT in clinical settings, particularly for individuals at risk of suicide. It highlights the importance of evidence-based therapeutic approaches in effectively managing and reducing suicidal ideation, ultimately contributing to better mental health outcomes for individuals undergoing this treatment.

The above finding agrees with Öst et al. (2015), whose study revealed that REBT interventions yielded higher effect sizes compared to waitlist or no treatment conditions, supporting its effectiveness in clinical populations. The finding is also in line with the finding of DiGiuseppe et al. (2016), which showed REBT's effectiveness across various populations, including adolescents and individuals with different psychiatric conditions, suggesting that its principles can be broadly applied.

The second finding revealed that there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants in the control group. This finding suggests that, without specific intervention, suicidal ideation and mental health awareness programmes remain relatively stable over the period of the study. This indicates that the participants' levels of suicidal thoughts did not naturally improve or worsen significantly in the absence of targeted treatment. Such a result underscores the necessity for active interventions to address and reduce suicidal ideation effectively.

This stability in suicidal ideation within the control group serves an important role in validating the effects of the interventions applied to the experimental groups. By demonstrating no significant change, it confirms that the reductions in suicidal ideation observed in the groups receiving REBT or mental health awareness programs are likely due to these specific treatments rather than external factors or the mere passage of time. Moreover, this finding highlights the potential risks of inaction. The fact that suicidal thoughts remained constant without intervention emphasizes the critical need for structured, evidence-based approaches to support individuals struggling with suicidal ideation. It reinforces the idea that, to effect meaningful change, proactive measures and therapeutic interventions are essential.

The above finding agrees with Goldney et al. (2008), who found that participants who did not receive any form of mental health intervention showed no significant changes in their mental health metrics over time. This reinforces the idea that suicidal ideation requires active engagement through therapeutic programs to initiate change. The finding is also in line with Thornicroft et al. (2015), who found that control groups are essential for validating the effectiveness of mental health interventions. The stability of suicidal ideation in the control group serves as a benchmark, demonstrating that without intervention, there is little to no fluctuation in mental health outcomes.

The third finding showed that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test suicidal ideation mean scores of participants exposed to REBT and the Control Group. The finding further revealed that students exposed to REBT treatment have a lower mean score. This finding suggests that the participants who received REBT treatment experienced a

considerable decline in suicidal ideation, whereas the control group did not show such improvement. Moreover, the finding that students exposed to REBT treatment have a lower mean score in post-test suicidal ideation compared to the control group underscores the efficacy of REBT in mitigating severe suicidal thoughts.

This result reinforces the notion that REBT, through its focus on identifying and challenging irrational beliefs, helps individuals develop healthier, more rational thought patterns. This cognitive restructuring can lead to a decrease in the intensity and frequency of suicidal ideation, as reflected in the lower mean scores for the REBT group. The comparison with the control group, which showed no significant change, emphasizes that the observed improvements in the REBT group are directly attributable to the therapeutic intervention rather than external factors or the mere passage of time. Furthermore, these findings support the broader application of REBT in clinical and educational settings as a valuable tool for addressing and reducing suicidal ideation among students. By demonstrating the significant impact of REBT compared to no intervention, the study highlights the critical importance of providing targeted mental health treatments to those in need. This evidence underscores the necessity of incorporating structured, evidence-based therapies like REBT into mental health programs to achieve meaningful reductions in suicidal thoughts and improve overall mental well-being.

The above finding agrees with DiGiuseppe et al. (2016) who found that REBT can lead to improvements in mental health outcomes, including reductions in suicidal thoughts. The finding also agrees with Öst et al. (2015), who found that cognitive-behavioral interventions

are effective in decreasing suicidal thoughts across various populations. This reinforces the notion that targeted therapeutic approaches can lead to meaningful improvements in mental health.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy (REBT) is effective in significantly reducing suicidal ideation among participants, as evidenced by the significant differences in pre-test and post-test mean scores. In contrast, the control group, which did not receive any specific intervention, showed no significant change in suicidal ideation, underscoring the necessity of targeted treatments. In view of this, the study recommended the following

1. Guidance Counsellors should expand the use of REBT in mental health services, particularly targeting individuals with high levels of suicidal ideation.
2. Guidance Counselors should integrate REBT into standard mental health care protocols and encourage its use in clinical practice for patients presenting with suicidal ideation.

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